

Cyclopentanone-2-carboxyanilide as a Gravimetric Reagent for Vanadium(IV)

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Vanadium(IV) (6-20 mg) has been precipitated from solutions of pH 5.0-6.0 with cyclopentanone-2-carboxyanilide and determined by weighing the complex, $\text{VO}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2$ after drying at 110° . Ag^+ , Tl^+ , Cr^{3+} , CrO_4^{2-} do not interfere with the determination and the interference due to Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Al^{3+} , Ce^{3+} , Zr^{4+} , WO_4^{2-} or MoO_4^{2-} has been prevented by using ammonium acetate or potassium iodide. The relative standard deviation is $\pm 0.23\%$.

CYCLOPENTANONE-2-carboxyanilide has been used for the determination of beryllium¹, uranium² and mercury³. In the present investigation vanadium(IV) has been estimated gravimetrically by weighing the complex $\text{VO}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2$ and separated from various metal ions. The reagent is stable and is appreciably soluble in water, and dilute ethanol. The complex is coagulated and filtered easily. Thus small quantities of vanadium(IV) can be determined rapidly with good degree of accuracy.

Experimental

Cyclopentanone-2-carboxyanilide solution: The reagent was prepared in the laboratory¹ and 0.4-0.5 g of it in 1-2 ml aqueous ethanol (65%) diluted to 10 ml with water was used for each determination. Alcohol was added to reduce the total volume of the reagent solution used for each determination.

Vanadium(IV) solution: Vanadyl sulphate (G. R., E. Merck) was dissolved in 0.05 M sulphuric acid and the vanadium content was estimated gravimetrically^{4,5}.

Diverse ions: Separate solutions of various metal ions were prepared in dilute acid. For this, nitrates of Ag^+ , Tl^+ , Cr^{3+} , Co^{2+} , Zr^{4+} , Ce^{3+} , sulphates of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and chlorides of Al^{3+} , Fe^{3+} and Hg^{2+} were taken. Sodium molybdate and tungstate solutions were also prepared. The metal contents were determined by conventional procedures.

Apparatus: A bench-model Cambridge pH-meter was used for the adjustment of pH. A pen-recording Aminco thermoanalyser was used for the thermal decomposition studies. A modified electrodynamic micro-balance⁶ was used for the measurement of magnetic susceptibility.

Procedure: A known volume of the standard vanadium(IV) solution containing 6-20 mg of vanadium was diluted to 150 ml with water, the pH was adjusted to 5.0-6.0 with 5% ammonium acetate solution and heated to 50° - 60° . The reagent (0.4-0.5 g) dissolved in 10 ml of approximately 10% (v/v) aqueous ethanol was added dropwise and the solution was well stirred. A light-blue precipitate was formed. The supernatant solution after the precipitation of the complex should be at least 0.1% with respect to cyclopentanone-2-carboxyanilide. The precipitate required less than 30 minutes to coagulate. It was filtered, washed with about 50 ml of hot water (50° - 60°) and dried at 110° to constant weight. The metal content was determined using the factor 0.1080. The results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE I—DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM(IV)

V taken, (mg)	Wt. of complex, (mg)		V found, (mg.)		Rel. Error, (%)	
6.5	60.2,	60.5	6.5 ₀	6.5 ₈	nil	+0.46
13.0	120.4,	120.0	13.0 ₀	12.9 ₆	nil	-0.30
20.5	190.0,	188.5	20.5 ₂	20.3 ₅	+0.09	-0.73

Results and Discussion

The vanadium(IV) cyclopentanone-2-carboxyanilide complex is light blue in colour and has appreciable solubility in common organic solvents.

A sample of the pure complex was analysed for vanadium by igniting a known weight of it to V_2O_5 and for nitrogen by Kjeldahl method. The experimental results, V 10.66, 10.78 (theor. 10.80) and N 5.87, 5.90% (theor. 5.94%) indicated the formula of the complex as $\text{VO}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2$.

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The magnetic susceptibility, χ_m was found to be 935.8×10^{-6} cgs unit and the magnetic moment, was 1.52 B.M. Thus the observed moment was marginally lower than the values for non-electrolytic oxovanadium(IV) complexes ($3d^1$: 1.6-1.8 B. M) with five coordinated square pyramidal structure, but not low enough to suggest any dimerisation.

Thermal decomposition studies showed that the complex was stable upto 165° and the decomposition which was complete at 490° recording a loss of 81.0% of weight. Formation of V_2O_5 by decomposition requires a loss of 80.71% in weight.

agents were added before the addition of the reagent and the mixture was boiled for a minute or two. The results of these separations are presented in Table 2.

The determination of vanadium(IV) was not possible in the presence of Pb^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Bi^3 and UO_2^{2+} .

Standard deviation : The relative standard deviation for 30 determinations of vanadium (containing 13.0 mg of the metal) with cyclopentanone-2-carboxyanilide was $\pm 0.23\%$

TABLE 2—SEPARATION OF VANADIUM(IV) FROM DIVERSE IONS. VANADIUM(IV) TAKEN : 13.00 mg.

Diverse Ions (mg)	Masking agent.	Wt. of complex (mg)		V found, (mg)		Rel. Error, (%)	
Ag ⁺ , 50	—	120.4,	120.5	13.0 ₀ ,	13.0 ₁	nil,	+0.07
Tl ⁺ , 50	—	120.3,	120.9	12.9 ₀ ,	13.0 ₀	-0.07,	+0.39
Cr ³⁺ , 50	—	120.0,	120.6	12.9 ₀ ,	13.0 ₀	-0.30,	+0.15
CrO ₄ ²⁻ , 50	—	120.3,	120.7	12.9 ₀ ,	13.0 ₀	-0.07,	+0.23
Cu ²⁺ , 50	a	120.1,	120.3	12.9 ₇ ,	12.9 ₀	-0.23,	-0.07
Ni ²⁺ , 50	a	120.2,	120.5	12.9 ₀ ,	13.0 ₁	-0.15,	+0.07
Co ²⁺ , 50	a	119.8,	120.3	12.9 ₀ ,	12.9 ₀	-0.53,	-0.07
Zn ²⁺ , 50	a	120.6,	120.3	13.0 ₀ ,	12.9 ₀	-0.15,	-0.07
Fe ³⁺ , 50	a	120.0,	120.3	12.9 ₀ ,	12.9 ₀	-0.30,	-0.07
Al ³⁺ , 50	a	119.6,	119.8	12.9 ₁ ,	12.9 ₀	-0.69,	-0.53
Zr ⁴⁺ , 50	a	120.3,	120.7	12.9 ₀ ,	13.0 ₀	-0.07,	+0.23
WO ₄ ²⁻ , 40	a	120.2,	120.5	12.9 ₀ ,	13.0 ₁	-0.15,	+0.07
Ce ³⁺ , 40	a	120.4,	120.7	13.0 ₀ ,	13.0 ₀	nil,	+0.23
Hg ²⁺ , 50	b	120.1,	120.3	12.9 ₇ ,	12.9 ₀	-0.23,	-0.07
MoO ₄ ²⁻ , 50	b	120.4,	120.2	13.0 ₀ ,	12.9 ₀	nil,	-0.15

(a) 5 ml of 5% ammonium acetate

(b) Potassium iodide (0.5 mg).

Effect of pH : Vanadium was precipitated at different pH-values adjusted with ammonium acetate (5%) solution maintaining all other conditions identical. The precipitation commenced at pH 3.0 and was quantitative between pH 5.0 and 6.0.

Effect of sequestering agents : It was observed that the presence of fluoride, citrate, tartrate, ethylenediamine tetraacetate, thioglycolic acid or ascorbic acid prevented the precipitation of the vanadium complex. However, acetate and iodide did not interfere.

Effect of diverse ions : There was no interference due to the presence of Ag⁺, Tl⁺, Cr³⁺ or CrO₄²⁻. Using 5 ml of a 5% ammonium acetate solution, separation of vanadium(IV) from Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Co²⁺, Zn²⁺, Fe³⁺, Al³⁺, Ce³⁺, Zr⁴⁺ or WO₄²⁻ was possible, while 0.5 g of potassium iodide was used to remove the interference due to Hg²⁺ and MoO₄²⁻. The masking

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References

1. N. K. CHAUDHURI and J. DAS, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1971, 57, 193.
2. S. K. MANDAL, N. K. CHAUDHURI and J. DAS, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1975, 80, 399.
3. N. K. CHAUDHURI and J. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (in press)
4. S. L. TZINBERG, *Zavodskaya Lab.*, 1933, 1, 18 ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1934, 28, 4334.
5. A. K. SARKAR and J. DAS, *Anal. Letters*, 1968, 1, 323.
6. D. NEOGY and R. B. LAL, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1971, 57, 193.